

IN VITRO SYNTHESIS OF BACTERIAL CELLULOSE/POLY(VINYL ALCOHOL) NANOCOMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Some bacteria such as *Gluconacetobacter* synthesize cellulose nanofibrils (BC) through the polymerization of glucose molecules. In static conditions, the nanofibrils form a three-dimensional network with a high absorption capacity. Recently, there has been an increasing interest in using nanocomposites based on BC nanofibrils and polymer matrices for biomedical applications. For these applications, it is highly desirable to fine-tune the properties of the scaffolds or implants to match the properties of the material that it intends to generate or replace [1].

Currently, nanocomposites can be developed by mixing bacterial cellulose nanofibrils in the wet state and polymer matrices. This method results in a significant improvement in mechanical properties of the matrix [2]. Biomimetic studies have motivated researchers to develop new materials in which the growth medium for BC is modified with water-soluble polymers allowing the *in vitro* assembling of the components and the development of nanocomposites with unique morphologies and properties [3]. However, the nanofiller/matrix ratio is difficult to determine because during purification, the polymer can be dissolved. In this work, as a solution to this problem, BC/poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) nanocomposites with controlled characteristics have been produced *in vitro* by physical linking and chemical crosslinking.

2. Experimental

The *Gluconacetobacter* strain used in this study was previously isolated from a pellicle from commercially homemade vinegar.

2.1. Physically crosslinked nanocomposites

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (Mw 89 000-98 000 and Mw 146.000-186.000, 99+% hydrolyzed) from Aldrich was added to Hestrin-Shramm (HS) medium (2%, w/v, glucose, 0.5%, w/v, peptone, 0.5%, w/v, yeast extract, 0.27%, w/v, Na₂HPO₄ and citric acid until pH 3.5) to concentration of 0, 2.5, 5 and 10 wt %. The modified media were autoclaved, inoculated and incubated for 10 days. The collected pellicles were processed through 6 freezing and thawing cycles between -20 and 20°C in a heated/refrigerated circulator with 6 h of holding time and thawing rates of 0.1°C/min. Crosslinked pellicles were washed with water and treated for 14 h in a 5 wt% KOH solution, rinsed until pH 7 and dried at 40 °C for 48 h to obtain films.

2.2. Chemically crosslinked nanocomposites

Before use, the strain was gradually exposed to the toxic crosslinking agent until the required concentration was achieved. Poly(vinyl alcohol) (146 000-186 000, 99+% hydrolyzed) from Aldrich was added to HS medium to a concentration of 0 and 3 wt%. A dialdehyde was used as a crosslinking agent at 10 wt% with respect to PVA and the pH solution was adjusted to 3.5 with phosphoric acid.

The modified media were autoclaved, inoculated and incubated for 10 days. The collected pellicles were cured into the oven at 120 °C for 5 min. Crosslinked pellicles were washed and dried as above described.

2.3. Nanocomposite characterization

The surface of bacterial cellulose and the nanocomposites was evaluated by scanning electronic microscopy in a Jeol JSM 5910 LV microscope operated at 10 kV. The ribbons nanofibrils were observed by transmission electron microscopy using a Philips CM200 microscope at 80 kV. The chemical structure was analyzed by attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy on a Nicolet 6700 spectrophotometer in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and an accumulation of 256 scans. Thermal stability was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis in a Mettler Toledo analyzer from room temperature to 800 °C at 10 °C/min and the mechanical behavior was determined with a Minimat 2000 microtension equipment according to ASTM D-882 standard using a load cell of 200 N at 5 mm/min.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1a. shows the three dimensional network of cellulose formed by nanosized ribbons (Fig. 1b) produced by bacteria at the surface of the liquid media. Nanocomposites with different reinforcement contents can be produced into the culture media during the cellulose synthesis. If water-soluble polymers are added in the medium, the nascent ribbons interact with the polymer and generate a composite material in which cellulose is homogeneously distributed throughout the matrix.

Fig. 1. Scanning (a) and transmission (b) electron microscopy images of bacterial cellulose ribbons.

In Fig. 2 photographs of the PVA/BC nanocomposite and the pure components are shown. The transparency of the matrix is not compromised even at different contents of bacterial cellulose. Due to the size effect, the nanofibrils network in the PVA matrix led to a very low loss of transparency of the original resin [4,5].

Likewise, Fig. 3 shows the surface topography of the matrix and the physically crosslinked nanocomposite films, respectively. Changes in surface topography of the matrix are observed due to the presence of homogeneously distributed cellulose nanofibrils produced by the bacteria. In the nanocomposites, larger pores are observed, which can be result in better performance in many biomedical applications including artificial blood vessels, scaffolding for tissue engineering of cartilage, and as wound dressing material for chronic wounds

FT-IR spectra recorded to identify physical linking and chemical crosslinking are presented in Fig. 4. Bands corresponding to PVA can be seen in the nanocomposite spectrum after purification steps, indicating that PVA is not solubilized and the crosslinking methods have been effective.

Fig. 2. Photographs of films of pure PVA (a), *in vitro* PVA/BC nanocomposite (b), and pure BC (c).

Fig. 3. Scanning electron microscopy images of the surface of a poly(vinyl alcohol) film (a) and a bacterial cellulose/poly(vinyl alcohol) nanocomposite surface with 5 wt% of BC (b).

Thermogravimetric analysis (Fig. 4) shows changes in the degradation temperature of the sample. Likewise, the presence of nanostructured network of cellulose nanofibrils increases the matrix thermal stability. This effect was more pronounced for the crosslinked nanocomposites by chemical way than physical linking. The presence of stronger covalent carbon-carbon bonds between PVA chains in the first case gives greater stability to nanocomposites than the physical interactions generated with the second method.

Stress-strain curves of nanocomposites and each of the components are shown in Fig. 6. An increase of Young's modulus with increasing amounts of cellulose nanofibrils within the matrix is observed.

Fig. 4. ATR-FTIR spectra of bacterial cellulose/poly(vinyl alcohol) nanocomposite: (a) physical crosslinking; (b) chemical crosslinked.

These results can be related to the three dimensional network of bacterial cellulose and its homogeneous distribution in the composite. A similar behavior was obtained for methyl cellulose and clay composites [6,7].

In conclusion, we have presented a new biotechnological tool to develop BC/PVA nanocomposites with a wide range of morphologies and compositions where the PVA is added into the culture medium for the cellulose nanofiber synthesis. The technique is an adequate procedure to produce nanocomposites that improve the mechanical performance of PVA, notably high strength and ductility.

Fig. 5. Thermogravimetry curves of pure components and crosslinked nanocomposite.

Fig. 6. Stress-strain curves of pure components and linked nanocomposites

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